

Pedagogical Architectures for the Development of Computational Thinking

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Abstract

Computational thinking is internationally recognized as an essential tool for solving problems in several areas of knowledge, and its inclusion in all levels of education is widely advocated. Although many initiatives have been undertaken in basic education, the discussion about applying computational thinking in higher education is still incipient. In order to enhance debate on the subject, we held an Advanced Seminar for students of an Informatics Applied to Education Doctoral Program, exploring the creation of Pedagogical Architectures (PA) that incorporate computational thinking into learning activities. Pedagogical architectures are understood as a pedagogical approach based on the articulations between constructivist theory, Paulo Freire's pedagogy, and the perspective of a Learning Ecology. These architectures involve mobile and reconfigurable articulations between open pedagogies, technologies, and organization of time and space, offering support to individual and collective learning processes. At the end of the seminar, the concept of a PA that fosters computational thinking in students of different levels of education and areas of knowledge was proposed to the participants, organized in groups. Subsequently, a peer review was carried out, in which each individual analyzed a proposal of another group. Conceptual reconstructions occurred in alternating individual and collective moments of action-reflection, seeking necessary consensus for developing PA proposals. Analysis of this Seminar endorses an aptitude of Pedagogical Architectures for promoting computational thinking in students. Each pedagogical architecture's ability to encourage computational thinking in students was analyzed, and results evidenced favorable and assorted scenarios for it.

Keywords: Computational Thinking; Pedagogical Architectures; Constructivism.

1 Introduction

Critical thinking training has been neglected at all levels of the educational system globally. Upon entering higher education, teachers perceive that previous school levels are not adequately preparing students for professional formation. Similarly, employers notice this unpreparedness in their new hires (ISTE, 2023).

In various countries worldwide, efforts are being made to reintroduce initiatives that ensure a more solid education in this fundamental aspect for personal development, life in general, and the world of work. Additionally, as this type of thinking is crucial in life and even for the learning process, supporting this development is essential in preparing citizens with an education more compatible with the competency demands inherent in problems in the modern world.

With the increasing availability of digital technologies, opportunities arise to tackle problems whose solutions can significantly alter our living experience in an increasingly complex world. We can include learning processes among our problems.

In this scenario, a new approach emerged in the first decade of the millennium to address problems: the exercise of computational thinking, which is increasingly seen as the gateway to reintegrating critical thinking into our problem-solving process.

In this article, we present an experiment on the design of new teaching proposals aimed at integrating interdisciplinary problem-solving practice, supported by digital technologies and underpinned by principles and strategies that can be applied universally across all fields of academic and professional knowledge. Resulting artifacts, devised as pedagogical architectures by the participants, were analyzed with respect to pedagogical and computational thinking rationale.

The article is organized into five sections. After this introduction, we present the theoretical framework supporting the conception and analysis of new approaches to the development of computational thinking, which are discussed in the following sections. In Section 3, we present a teaching experiment using Pedagogical Architectures to develop Computational Thinking. In Section 4, we analyze student productions, and in Section 5, we show the final considerations about the experiment.

2 Theoretical Framework

This section presents some concepts needed to support the design and analysis of Pedagogical Architectures for developing Computational Thinking.

2.1 Computational thinking

Education, at all levels, aims to prepare citizens to a) solve problems relevant to the well-being of humanity, b) critically analyze situations to enable decision-making, and c) acquire new concepts. It is not only about applying known models to similar situations; it is necessary to develop the ability to find new solutions to problems, using resources that contribute to social or economic gains and thus finding solutions to new problems (Sternberg, 1986; Piaget, 1972).

The pursuit of systematizing an education that favors the preparation of human beings to achieve the objectives mentioned above is quite ancient and has become known as "critical thinking." This pursuit dates back to antiquity with founders such as Plato and Aristotle. In modern times, John Dewey (1933) is considered to have assumed this role. According to recent studies (Kules, 2016), the concern for developing critical thinking has gradually been set aside in the educational process, which has been a cause for concern in many countries.

Running parallel to initiatives to reintegrate critical thinking into the educational context (Sternberg, 1986; Kules, 2016), we saw the emergence in 2006 of a related concept called Computational Thinking (Wing, 2006), which has mobilized numerous institutions around the world to integrate Computational Thinking into the educational system at all levels. The current literature is extensive, both by enthusiasts and critics. The text presented by Wing (2006) profoundly impacted academic minds worldwide. As a result of these initiatives, we can find resources ranging from pedagogical resources to proposals for integrating computational thinking into the curriculum.

While Computational Thinking has been interpreted by many as a set of strategies to support problem-solving in any area of human knowledge, others have interpreted it as the creation of systems whose outcome is the development of algorithms that human and not human agents can execute. It is usual to see an emphasis on learning to program in different programming languages, many of which are 'block'-based. We find important computational thinking strategies in the specialized literature known as its "pillars." The following stand out: Abstraction, Decomposition, Pattern Recognition, and Algorithms (Rao, Bhagat; 2024). The Abstraction pillar refers to the strategy of considering only the essential characteristics of objects; Decomposition consists of identifying simpler sub-problems that facilitate the resolution of the main problem; Pattern Recognition refers to the identification of relevant patterns or trends to understand the problem, and finally, Algorithms refer to establishing a sequence of steps to achieve a particular end.

Although criticisms can be found regarding this reduction of studies on the development of critical thinking (Easterbrooks, 2014), we can understand that the success of initiatives supported by them, and some others more cited, favor the resumption of a tradition of training people to use problem-solving strategies.

2.2 Pedagogical Architectures

Digital technologies have aroused the interest of researchers, teachers, and the general public in supporting the production of digital materials and social communication. Forty years after the emergence of computers, the Internet has reached many people worldwide. Throughout the same period, research in Artificial Intelligence explored various methodologies, resulting in significant advancements that are currently applicable in the educational field. At the dawn of the new millennium, the Internet began to be accessed from mobile devices. Along with these technological innovations, many others emerged. All these contributions were noticed by those interested in the production and dissemination of content, as well as in the creation of environments to foster social interactions.

Many initiatives to promote education emerged—first, the so-called educational software, followed by learning objects and learning management systems. However, the use of these tools in the school context continued with low integration into the daily life of the classroom.

More recently, a movement initiated in the late 19th century, Ferriere's New School, characterized by the student's active participation in their learning process, has returned to the agenda, this time labeled as active methodologies. This return is mainly due to the possibilities provided by new media for the production of interactive objects, digital communication mechanisms, and the advent of mobile Internet and smartphones (Hartikainen et al., 2019).

However, it is not enough one's desire to adopt the concept of active methodologies in school practice; a methodological approach that favors the engagement of teachers and students in new practices is necessary. Therefore, it is essential to have theoretical foundations that provide the necessary support for adopting active methodologies. Today, we can find several examples of active methodologies in the academic literature that are not always supported by digital technologies and appropriate theoretical frameworks (Hartikainen et al., 2019).

As learning situations vary and solutions depend on the content's nature and the classroom context's specifics, more is needed than a repertoire of methodologies. The teacher cannot be satisfied with being a mere implementer of practices proposed by others that do not always fit their specific situation. In addition to a good repertoire, it is essential to be given the freedom to create.

With this intention, the Pedagogical Architectures framework was conceived, a theoretical-methodological support for designing new active methodologies anchored in Jean Piaget's constructivism (Piaget, 1968) and Paulo Freire's Pedagogy of Questioning. The proposal is also based on a new conception of time and space, adoption of the Internet as an actual development platform, Virtual Learning Environments, and Artificial Intelligence Tools (Carvalho, Aragón, Menezes, 2005; Aragón, 2016; Menezes & Aragón, 2018; Menezes et al. 2021). The conception of Pedagogical Architectures considers the following pedagogical principles:

1. Educating towards the search for solutions to real (everyday) problems;
2. Educating so that individuals are able to transform information into knowledge;
3. Educating to encourage authorship, interlocution, and the use of different languages;
4. Educating to build autonomy and cooperation;
5. Educating to promote investigating and reflective subjects.

Some elements can be highlighted for a better understanding of this framework:

- Piaget's constructivism ensures that the teacher's role is not that of someone who gives lectures but rather someone who offers work proposals to the students, problematizes, and provides support for the advancement of students in their quest for knowledge construction (Becker, 2001);
- Educational activities aim to explore the objects of study by the students, sometimes individually, sometimes in cooperation, always supported by their prior knowledge, which will enable them to anchor new knowledge;
- The materials to be explored, as well as the problems to be solved, should be based on the student's interests, preferably supported by their demands;
- There is no need for activities to be carried out only in the classroom space or at a specific time. The use of the Internet offers the possibility of asynchronous cooperation. Everyone's work, whenever possible and desirable, can be carried out from different places. Materials, authoring environments, and student productions might be hosted in 'the cloud' so that everyone (teacher and students) can access them from anywhere (provided they have internet access);
- Tedious or mostly operational activities, low on intellectual work, both for the teacher and the students, can be carried out with the support of artificial intelligence and other support software;
- Intellectual activities should always aim to develop thinking triggered by the cognitive imbalances needed to lead students to reach new equilibrium levels.

2.3 Pedagogical Architectures and the development of the Computational Thinking

Computational Thinking is not a simple content that should be taught but rather a problem-solving competency that individuals need to develop. This competency is based on a repertoire of strategies (pillars) that can be used to seek solutions to a problem. Furthermore, it constitutes an interdisciplinary skill.

We understand that a Pedagogical Architecture should always provide opportunities for students to develop computational thinking. The student's development will come from seeking the appropriate strategy to solve a given situation at each point.

3 A Teaching Experiment

To carry out an in-depth study of the relationship between Pedagogical Architectures and the development of computational thinking, we planned and conducted an Advanced Seminar titled "Pedagogical Architectures for Computational Thinking Development." That 60-hour seminar was distributed over weekly sessions of 4 hours each. Participants were all PhD students from the Informatics in Education Graduate Program at the Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, in Brazil. Five of them are men and two are women, aged between 25 to 45 years old with no previous knowledge about the seminar contents. The seminar was developed based on Pedagogical Architectures. The conceptual appropriation was based on the Pedagogical Architecture of "Cooperative Reading," (Müller et al, 2021) which involved reading and summarizing articles, followed by a peer review of the document produced by participants from previous readings. The summaries and reviews were recorded in a virtual learning environment. After each cooperative reading, sessions were held to debate individual positions on the content of the readings.

Following the reading of foundational texts on Pedagogical Architectures and Computational Thinking, an activity was conducted to analyze two Pedagogical Architectures to investigate whether there was evidence of their potential to support the development of Computational Thinking. Two Pedagogical Architectures, "Learning Projects" and "Thesis Debate" (Menezes, Castro-Jr, Aragón, 2021) were analyzed. In this assessment, students identified pedagogical principles as the basis for the Pedagogical Architectures and attributed a high

potential for these architectures for the development of Computational Thinking. After completing this activity, debates were held to share the participants' perceptions within the teams.

Subsequently, two teams were formed, with a different composition from the first ones. The teams were asked to design Pedagogical Architectures aimed at developing Computational Thinking in school contexts. Each team had the autonomy to choose the target audience and the architecture theme. The proposals were documented and made available for reading and analysis by each participant in the class. The participants from each team read and provided documented feedback on the other group's proposal.

This activity ran concurrently with new cooperative reading activities, addressing advanced aspects of Pedagogical Architectures and Computational Thinking. At the end of the activities, each participant produced an individual report reflecting on their learnings derived from the readings and activities involving analyzing known architectures and producing new architectures.

4 Analysis Results

The analysis was conducted to elucidate *whether or not* and *how* the two groups of students in the seminar utilized the theoretical foundations and possibilities for developing Computational Thinking (CT) in the architectures created. During the seminar, before elaborating a pedagogical architecture proposal, students evaluated existing architectures such as "Learning Projects" and "Thesis Debate". In that evaluation, students identified pedagogical principles serving as the basis for the Pedagogical Architectures (PAs) and attributed a high potential of these architectures for CT.

The data evaluated consisted of writings produced by the two groups, with references to activities at each stage of the pedagogical architectures. Firstly, each stage was analyzed to gather evidence of the relationship between those activities and their rationale. After this analysis, the pedagogical architectures were evaluated as a whole, aiming at identifying which pedagogical principles and CT pillars were considered/valued when designing proposals. For the analysis of the architectures developed by the students, two categories were defined as follows:

Category 1 - Pedagogical Principles: Use of the "Constructivism" and "Freirean Theory" learning theories in the student group's PA proposal. Drawing upon the work of Carvalho, Nevado, and Menezes (2005), we considered the articulations between constructivism and Freirean theory, synthesized into five pedagogical principles, as previously presented in Section 2.2.

Category 2 - CT Pillars: Use of the four Pillars of Computational Thinking that are evident in different stages of the architecture. Each stage may emphasize certain pillars, depending on the proposed action. The pillars considered are (a) Abstraction, (b) Decomposition, (c) Pattern Recognition, and (d) Algorithm, as presented in Section 2.1.

The following are the analyses of the pedagogical architectures devised by the two groups. After a brief description of each one, a table summarizes found relationships between pedagogical principles and CT pillars (categories 1 and 2). Relationships are grouped according to action developed at a certain stage of each PA.

4.1 Analysis of the Pedagogical Architecture Proposed by Group 1

Title: Problem Solving for the UNESCO BR Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) List

General Description of the Proposed PA: The PA proposed by Group 1 involves working with students in the final grades of Elementary School on the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to construct

solutions for problems. The proposal can be adapted according to a teacher's intentions and the specifics of each class for application in other educational stages.

Pedagogical Principles Considered in Various Stages of the Architecture: The proposed architecture starts from the central idea of the need for interaction with the objects of study and among students, which is addressed from the early stages, as illustrated in stages 1, 2, and 3, where students participate in choosing one of the UN SDGs to be worked on in the PA. Real problem-solving, experienced by the students, begins in Stage 1 when the study object (SDGs) is defined.

The principle that predominated in the organization of the PA was "educating to promote autonomy and cooperation" (principle 4), showing recognition of the importance of cooperative learning for students' knowledge advancement. Also, "educating to encourage authorship, interlocution, and the use of different languages" was presented significantly. The principle of "educating to promote inquiry-minded and reflective individuals" is explicit in the final stages, indicating that the student authors of the PA conceive it based on cooperative learning, authorship, and dialogue.

Aspects of CT Pillars Privileged in Various Stages of the Architecture: Aspects of CT Pillars Privileged in Various Stages of the Architecture: The student authors of the PA considered that the proposal involves all four pillars of CT, with an emphasis on abstraction. The organization of tasks considered, the need for pattern recognition for problem formulation, data collection, and analysis. The demand for decomposition skills and algorithm usage arises explicitly from the stage of constituting an interdisciplinary approach to problem-solving.

Table 1. Summarizes the relationships the group of student authors established between the stages of the proposed pedagogical architecture, the considered pedagogical principles, and the CT postulates.

Table 1. Survey of relationships established between the stages, pedagogical principles, and CT pillars.

Stages	Action	Pedagogical Principles	CT Pillars
Stage 1	Choice of one of the UN SDGs	(1) solutions to real (everyday) problems (4) development of autonomy and cooperation	Abstraction Pattern recognition
Stage 2	Selection of topics to be addressed	(1) solutions to real (everyday) problems (4) development of autonomy and cooperation	Abstraction Pattern recognition
Stage 3	Group formation	(4) development of autonomy and cooperation	Pattern recognition Algorithm
Stage 4	Interdisciplinary approach	(2) to transform information into knowledge (3) authorship, interlocution, and the use of different languages	Abstraction Pattern Recognition Decomposition Algorithm
Stage 5	Inter-group dialogue	(3) authorship, interlocution, and the use of different languages (4) development of autonomy and cooperation	Abstraction Pattern Recognition Decomposition Algorithm
Stage 6	Analysis, discussion, and peer critique	(4) the development of autonomy and cooperation (5) to promote investigating and reflective subjects	Abstraction Pattern Recognition Decomposition Algorithm
Stage 7	Final work development	(3) authorship, interlocution, and the use of different languages (4) development of autonomy and cooperation (5) to promote investigating and reflective subjects	Abstraction Pattern Recognition Decomposition Algorithm
Stage 8	Presentation of developed works	(3) authorship, interlocution, and the use of different languages (4) development of autonomy and cooperation (5) to promote investigating and reflective subjects	Abstraction Pattern recognition

4.2 Analysis of the Pedagogical Architecture proposed by Group 2

Title: Problem-Solving using Educational Robotics Elements

General Description of the Proposed PA: This pedagogical architecture uses educational robotics to foster and develop computational thinking in students, emphasizing teamwork and knowledge construction through investigation and real problem-solving.

Pedagogical Principles Considered in Various Stages of the Architecture: Similar to PA1, the central idea of interacting with study objects and addressing real problems is emphasized from the early stages, where students interact with various sources of information and define a problem to be addressed in the PA. The main principle considered by students in architecture involved "educating to promote inquiry-minded and reflective individuals," aligning with the broader objectives of PAs. They also prominently identified the principle of "educating to encourage authorship, interlocution, and the use of different languages," followed by the postulate on autonomy and cooperation. The organization of the PA allows us to observe that students have incorporated all five pedagogical principles into their proposal, indicating an understanding of these principles that have been translated into various stages of the PA.

Aspects of CT Pillars in Various Stages of the Architecture: The student authors of the PA considered that the proposal involves abstraction, task organization into smaller parts, pattern recognition, and algorithm usage in most stages. According to the student authors, the students to whom the PA will be applied (targeted for an age range of 13-14 years) will enhance their teamwork, reflection, and analysis skills, which will undoubtedly propel knowledge construction. Only algorithm usage skills are not included in the stages of problem definition, analysis of works, and evaluation of the results of the proposed PA.

Table 2. Survey of relationships established between the stages, pedagogical principles, and CT pillars for PA2.

Stages	Action	Pedagogical Principles	CT Pillars
Stage 1	Students research a topic of interest and develop a problem to be solved.	(1) solutions to real (everyday) problems (5) to promote investigating and reflective subjects	Abstraction Pattern Recognition Decomposition
Stage 2	Reflecting on the problem situation at hand, identifying and planning its solution.	(3) authorship, interlocution, and the use of different languages (5) to promote investigating and reflective subjects	Abstraction Pattern Recognition Decomposition Algorithm
Stage 3	Execution of actions.	(2) to transform information into knowledge (3) authorship, interlocution, and the use of different languages (4) development of autonomy and cooperation (5) to promote investigating and reflective subjects	Abstraction Pattern Recognition Decomposition Algorithm
Stage 4	Verification/validation of the solution.	(3) authorship, interlocution, and the use of different languages (5) to promote investigating and reflective subjects	Abstraction Pattern Recognition Decomposition Algorithm
Stage 5	Visiting and analyzing the productions of other groups.	(3) authorship, interlocution, and the use of different languages (4) development of autonomy and cooperation (5) to promote investigating and reflective subjects	Abstraction Pattern recognition Decomposition
Stage 6	Construction of the final prototype.	(2) to transform information into knowledge (3) authorship, interlocution, and the use of different languages	Abstraction Pattern recognition Decomposition Algorithm
Stage 7	Participatory evaluation.	(5) to promote investigating and reflective subjects	Abstraction Pattern recognition
Stage 8	Presentation of the product, considering the evaluation conducted in the previous stage.	(4) development of autonomy and cooperation (5) to promote investigating and reflective subjects	Abstraction Pattern recognition Decomposition

5 Concluding Remarks

The two architectures proposed by the students allowed us to identify, albeit with different emphases, the presence of all five principles that support them theoretically and pedagogically. The stages that make up the architectures, as a whole, showed that the students were able to transform these principles into authorial pedagogical practices, which presented different possibilities for configuring a PA. The focus of the proposed PAs can illustrate these differences. While PA1 emphasizes the principle of educating for the construction of autonomy and cooperation, PA2 appears more supported by the idea of forming inquiry-minded and reflective individuals. However, although these PAs presented some differences regarding a greater focus on some of the principles, this does not constitute dissonances but rather variations since the pedagogical principles encompass the same idea of promoting knowledge construction. It can also be emphasized that the PAs were elaborated to consider an ecological perspective of learning, in which the pedagogical principles, practices, resources, times, and learning spaces are interrelated components forming a "framework" or structuring support for cognitive constructions.

From the standpoint of the four pillars of Computational Thinking, we can observe that they are present in all stages of the proposed architectures. We highlight that the Abstraction pillar appears in almost all stages of the two architectures. This finding is consistent with the importance of abstraction in all activities we undertake. Next comes the Decomposition pillar, which is also compatible with its role in problem-solving, identifying sub-problems that facilitate various aspects of a solution. Lastly, the Algorithm pillar appears to have a precise role in determining steps to organize the flow of tasks and generally appears in the final stage of developing a solution.

Although our observations were limited to a specific context (teachers devising new pedagogical proposals), the analysis results are promising, as participants have been able to appropriate the seminar contents and demonstrate their willingness to use the Pedagogical Architectures Framework as a conceptual tool in designing embodying CT aspects. Future work on design of teaching proposals based upon pedagogical architectures and computational thinking, might include groups from other knowledge areas and education levels. Further work should also focus on solutions for specific and complex issues like students with special educational needs or sustainable solutions for small communities.

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